

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

**Deliverable D7.6: Training & user onboarding activities report
(interim)**

30/04/2021

 Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D7.6		
Document Title	Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)		
Due Date	30-APR-2021	Delivery Date	13-MAY-2021
Lead Beneficiary	INAF		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA, ALTEC, GARR, INNOMINE, RICOH, UBREMEN, UOP, CITE, SZTAKI		
Editor(s)	C. Bordiu, C. Pino (INAF)		
Authors (s)	Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Eva Sciacca (INAF), Josep Quintana (CORONIS), Katalin Kovacs (INNOMINE), Alessandro Tibaldi (UNIMIB), Ricardo Vitorino (UBIWHERE), Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA)		
Contributor (s)	Claudio Pisa (GARR), Danai Lampridou (NKUA), Mel Krokos (UoP), Giorgos Papanikos (CITE), Jozsef Kovacs (SZTAKI), Eleni Petra (NKUA), Attilas Farkas (SZTAKI), Simone Mantovani (MEE0), Laura Vettorello (MEE0), Thomas Ceconello (UNIMIB)		
Reviewer(s)	Stergios Kokorotsikos (EUNICE)		
Workpackages	WP7		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Complete
Version details	Revision: 308 . Last save: 2021-05-13 , 10:58 Pages: 28 . Characters: 39.961		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	EOSC, Security, Underwater Research, Planetary Science, Astrophysics, Atmospheric Research,		

Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	13/05/2021	Document final version	C. Bordiu	

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners

that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Document Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	7
Abstract	8
1. Introduction	9
2. Internal Training Activities	10
2.1. Open Science and Open Access	10
2.1.1. Introduction to RDM, ARGOS for DMPs.....	10
2.1.2. Open access publications.....	10
2.1.3. Research Data Management.....	11
2.1.4. RDM – Services: supporting FAIR data and management	11
2.1.5. The Zenodo long-term digital preservation repository.....	11
2.2. EOSC Training and Onboarding	11
2.2.1. Presentation of the NEANIAS service model.....	12
2.2.2. EOSC onboarding and service management procedures	12
2.2.3. Involvement into EOSC Secretariat.....	12
2.2.4. Participation in EOSC-hub week 2020 seminars.....	12
2.2.5. Participation in ESFRI-EOSC workshop 2020	13
2.2.6. Participation in the EOSC Symposium	13
2.3. Training on NEANIAS Core services.....	13
2.3.1. AAI.....	13
2.3.2. Logging	14
2.3.3. Accounting.....	14
2.3.4. GARR Cloud training: OpenStack, Docker and Kubernetes.....	14
2.3.5. Applied Kubernetes webinar.....	15
2.3.6. Service monitoring / Internal (nagios).....	15
2.3.7. Monitoring / External (Argo).....	15
2.3.8. Short trainings on plenary and technical board meetings	15
2.4. Thematic Services Internal Validation	17
3. External Onboarding and Training Activities	18
3.1. User board coordination	18
3.2. Thematic Services Onboarding and Training	18
3.2.1. Underwater specific activities.....	18

Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)

3.2.2.	<i>Atmospheric specific activities</i>	19
3.2.3.	<i>Space specific activities</i>	21
3.3.	Core Services Onboarding	23
3.4.	Business opportunities and innovation (Open Call).....	24
4.	Conclusions and Future Steps	26
	References	27
	List of acronyms	28

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

No table of figures entries found.

Document Tables

Table 1: The Number of Applications per Thematic Sector – First round of Open Call

24

Abstract

The objective of deliverable D7.6 is to report on the training and user onboarding activities carried out in NEANIAS. In this document we report the internal training activities aimed at project members, focusing on the introduction of open science practices, EOSC way of working, and capacity building sessions on core services. Then, we present the onboarding and training strategy for external users, covering the activities delivered and foreseen by the thematic work packages, such as specific webinars and participation in international events, as well as the actions related to the first NEANIAS Open Call for Innovation.

1. Introduction

One of the most critical aspects in NEANIAS is the **delivery of training and capacity building activities for researchers, engineers and innovators**, both internal and external to the project. In particular, the NEANIAS roadmap foresees the organization and management of specific sessions and related materials on the following topics:

- *Open Science and EOSC / EOSC hub coaching*, for researchers primarily aboard the project as well as outsiders, especially under the perspective of EOSC hub and NEANIAS service portfolio.
- *Open Access coaching*, for project participants.
- *EOSC coaching*, for developers internal to the project or external coming from Open Innovation Calls and synergies established.
- *Training and coaching on NEANIAS services exploitation*, for end-users (researchers, industry and innovators), including core and thematic services.

The technical materials required for such sessions are assembled from **the inputs provided by the relevant work packages**, being tailored to the particular scope of each session. Capacity building in the project employs multiple means and tools, such as webcasts, webinars, online training platforms, social media, workshops and meetings.

Training, user onboarding and capacity building activities are crucial for the long-term sustainability of the project, largely contributing to visibility, dissemination, facilitating the engagement of end user communities, and gathering insightful feedback for the Technical and Strategy boards. This document describes the **current status and future plans for user onboarding, training and capacity building activities in NEANIAS**. It is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the internal training and capacity building activities; Section 3 covers the carried out and planned activities for onboarding and training external users; and Section 4 presents the conclusions and future steps.

2. Internal Training Activities

In the course of the project, a number of training and capacity building activities targeted to internal users -users directly involved in the project or members of the partner institutions and companies- have been carried out. The goal of these activities is threefold: (1) to **introduce the Open Science paradigm**, with a particular emphasis on FAIR practices, and present the EOSC ecosystem and the role of NEANIAS within that ecosystem; (2) to support service providers and project developers by **facilitating the integration of core and thematic services**, through tutorials, technical sessions and example use cases; and (3) to evaluate the maturity of the services by involving **internal domain experts in validation sessions**. These activities, coordinated by the relevant Work Packages, have played a fundamental role in pushing the NEANIAS service portfolio to its current state of stability and maturity (most services already TRL7 at least).

2.1. Open Science and Open Access

The first set of activities comprised **five specialized webinars about Open Science practices** mainly targeted at researchers onboard the project as well as outsiders, especially under the perspective of EOSC hub and NEANIAS service offerings.

2.1.1. Introduction to RDM, ARGOS for DMPs

This webinar focused on Data Management Plans. It started with an **introduction to Research Data Management** and what a Data Management Plan is, and then went on to introduce ARGOS, the OpenAIRE Data Management Plan preparation service.

- Date: Feb 21st, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [Data Management Plans](#)

2.1.2. Open access publications

This webinar **introduced Open Access for publications**, its advantages for researchers, and the “Green and Gold” routes to open access¹, as defined in the Budapest Open Access Initiative Declaration.

- Date: July 10th, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [Open Access](#)

¹ <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/about/green-or-gold-routes-to-oa>

2.1.3. Research Data Management

This webinar went into **details on Research Data Management, with regard to Policies, Lifecycles, and Plans**. It presented the necessity for Open Data in the H2020 context, the requirement for a Data Management Plan, and then went into details of Research Data Management, such as actors, requirements, lifecycles, processes, etc. It also presented the vision for the integration of NEANIAS outputs into OpenAIRE.

- Date: February 3rd, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [RDM Training](#)

2.1.4. RDM – Services: supporting FAIR data and management

This webinar went into **advice and best practices on how to apply FAIR for the NEANIAS services**, including a summary of requirements, a checklist to follow for repositories, and practical advice.

- Date: February 10th, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenters: Ellie Papadopoulou (ATHENA, OperAIRE), Iryna Kutchma (OpenAIRE)
- Available training material and recording: [RDM Training - Applying FAIR](#)

2.1.5. The Zenodo long-term digital preservation repository

This webinar focused on **the use of Zenodo as a long-term, catch-all, digital preservation repository for research outputs coming from the NEANIAS project**. Zenodo as a repository service was introduced first, then its REST API was presented as a means for service providers to upload their research data. Finally, new and upcoming functionality of Zenodo was presented, such as the ability to create custom metadata attributes based on well-established schemas.

- Date: March 18th, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenters: Alex Ioannidis (Zenodo)
- Available training material and recording: [Zenodo Training](#)

2.2. EOSC Training and Onboarding

The second set of activities dealt with **EOSC coaching and training**, so NEANIAS service providers become familiar with EOSC standards, procedures and practices. These activities

involved a series of webinars, informative sessions and events that provided insights on the EOSC ecosystem.

2.2.1. Presentation of the NEANIAS service model

In this dedicated session, NEANIAS service providers were presented with the **standard EOSC service model**. The Provider and Resource profiles were introduced by means of practical examples, along with specific support to complete the relevant data sheets for a successful onboarding.

- Date: December 17th, 2020.
- Presenter: Christos Tsiakaliaris (ATHENA)
- Available training material: [EOSC service model](#) and [EOSC definitions](#)

2.2.2. EOSC onboarding and service management procedures

This special training session presented the **stages of the EOSC service onboarding process**. Afterwards, it went on to introduce the service management toolset, comprising the NEANIAS service catalogue², the NEANIAS ticketing system, and the NEANIAS wiki, plus additional service-specific tools. Then, the service management processes and incident handling procedures were explained in detail.

- Date: March 10th, 2021
- Presenter: Christos Tsiakaliaris (ATHENA)
- Available training material: [EOSC Onboarding](#) and [Service management](#)

2.2.3. Involvement into EOSC Secretariat

NEANIAS Project Manager Eleni Petra became member of the EOSC Training and Skills Working Group of the EOSC secretariat, with the goal of building competence and capabilities for EOSC, providing a sustainable training infrastructure to support EOSC and ensure its uptake. Similarly, NEANIAS Technical Manager Georgios Kakalettris became member and the Architecture Working Group, aiming at providing a technical framework suitable to enable and sustain an evolving EOSC federation of system, including standards, APIs and protocols.

2.2.4. Participation in EOSC-hub week 2020 seminars

Representatives from all NEANIAS Work Packages **attended the EOSC Hub Week 2020**³, a three-day event held between May 18th-20th with more than 800 participants. The event brought together partners, key players and stakeholders from the EOSC network, with the

² <https://catalogue.neanias.eu/>

³ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/eosc-hub-week-2020-goes-virtual>

goal of **aligning efforts and exploiting synergies for a successful and sustainable materialization of the EOSC ecosystem**. In a series of plenary sessions, seminars and technical workshops, the strategic EOSC vision, along with useful insights and best practices concerning EOSC service onboarding and data management, were provided.

2.2.5. Participation in ESFRI-EOSC workshop 2020

NEANIAS participated in the 2nd edition of the workshop on the connection of ESFRI Research Infrastructures to EOSC, which took place on October 6th and 7th, 2020. This event brought together ESFRI and EOSC stakeholders to **showcase added-value concepts for users and providers, with concrete use cases, good practices and novel approaches to Open Science** and cross-domain data sharing within the EOSC framework. Besides, new tools for thematic providers were presented, concerning networking, computing and data services.

2.2.6. Participation in the EOSC Symposium

NEANIAS took part in the EOSC Symposium between October 19th and 22nd, an interdisciplinary event organised by the EOSC Executive & Governing Board with the support of the EOSC Secretariat. This milestone event, brought together researchers, data scientist, infrastructure providers, EOSC projects and representatives from the EU member countries in a unique opportunity to discuss the final steps toward **the implementation materialisation of a first version of a fully-fledged European Open Science Cloud**. In particular, the event covered the highlights of EOSC during the first two years after launch, focusing on lessons learnt and outlining the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

2.3. Training on NEANIAS Core services

Core services constitute **one of the pillars of the NEANIAS architecture**, providing a traversal, general-purpose, and reusable infrastructure that supports a number of functionalities (e.g., Authentication, Accounting...) to be exploited by higher-level thematic services. A series of capacity building technical sessions organised by the Core service providers are planned or have already been conducted, with the aim of **supporting Thematic Service providers in the integration process according to the NEANIAS development roadmap**. The sessions include architectural specifications, hands-on demonstrations and practical use cases.

2.3.1. AAI

This event **introduced the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)** service, introduced also the OpenID Connect protocol that it supports, and gave specific instructions to the service providers on how to successfully integrate with it.

Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)

- Date: September 17th, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Giorgos Papanikos (CITE)
- Training material and recording: [AAI Demo & Q&A Session](#)

2.3.2. Logging

This session **introduced the Logging service as deployed and configured for the NEANIAS project** and gave instructions to service providers on how to properly integrate with it. The user interface of the Logging service was also demonstrated.

- Date: October 29th, 2020
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Giorgos Papanikos (CITE)
- Training material and recording: [Logging Service Demo](#)

2.3.3. Accounting

This webinar **introduced the Accounting service as implemented for the NEANIAS project**. Its relationship with the *Logging* service was presented, and instructions were given to service providers on how to properly integrate with it. The user interface of the accounting service was also demonstrated.

- Date: January 29th, 2021
- Duration: 1 hour
- Presenter: Stratis Giannopoulos (CITE)
- Training material and recording: [Accounting Logging Demo](#)

2.3.4. GARR Cloud training: OpenStack, Docker and Kubernetes

This 2-hour long session, in the form of a webinar, **introduced three aspects of the cloud offerings at GARR**. It started with an overview of **Openstack** and a demonstration of its front-end. It continued with an introduction of **Docker**, as a means to package and deploy applications. Finally, it concluded with an introduction and demonstration of **Kubernetes**, which is the most recent addition to the GARR cloud offerings. In the GARR deployment of Kubernetes, the latter uses Docker as the container engine and this is why Docker was also presented in this webinar.

- Date: September 29th, 2020
- Duration: 2 hours
- Presenters: Claudio Pisa, Alberto Colla, Alex Barchiesi, Matteo Di Fazio, Delia Passalacqua, Marco Lorini (GARR)
- Training material and recording: [Garr Cloud training webinar](#)

2.3.5. Applied Kubernetes webinar

This webinar focused in more detail in **the use of Kubernetes to deploy services at GARR**. It was deemed necessary as the Kubernetes technology was selected by many thematic service providers as the “new” way to deploy their services to make optimal use of the resources available to them at GARR, and due to the steep learning curve of the Kubernetes system. In this one and a half hours session, the basics of Kubernetes were reintroduced, an existing NEANIAS service (U3, *uw-map*) was showcased as it moved from Docker on a VM to a Kubernetes deployment, and the batch Jobs as supported by Kubernetes were surveyed.

- Date: April 14th, 2021
- Duration: 1.5 hours
- Presenters: Nikos Chondros, Michalis Konstantopoulos (NKUA)
- Training material and recording: [Applied Kubernetes](#)

2.3.6. Service monitoring / Internal (nagios)

This is a webinar that is currently in the planning stage. It revolves around **the NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure**, based on Nagios, InfluxDB, Prometheus and Grafana, and advice on how service providers can take full advantage of it to monitor their service from an “internal” point of view, including network availability and even operating system status regarding security upgrades.

2.3.7. Monitoring / External (Argo)

This is a webinar that is currently in the planning stage. It will present **the Argo monitoring service**, which is already an EOSC service, and advice on how service providers can prepare “probes” that will allow Argo to monitor their service’s “health”, and how they can in turn get metrics on its availability. This will monitor the services from the “outside”, from the user’s point of view.

2.3.8. Short trainings on plenary and technical board meetings

Besides the capacity building sessions, a number of **short complementary demonstrations** were conducted during the NEANIAS 3rd Plenary Meeting, held on November 19-20th, 2020, and during the 3rd Technical Board meeting on January 22th, 2021 (recordings available [here](#)). These demonstrations were mostly live sessions, not exceeding 10 minutes and focusing on **practical aspects related to core services implementation and use**. The contents of these live demos are summarized below:

2.3.8.1. Portal and Catalogue

This short session introduced a preliminary **working version of the NEANIAS service catalogue**, showcasing the site structure and the service browsing and filtering functionalities.

- Date: November 20th, 2020
- Presenter: George Papastefanatos (ATHENA)

2.3.8.2. Logging service

This live demonstration focused on the **integration with the NEANIAS logging service**, presenting a simulated service integration that highlighted the most relevant technical aspects to be considered to successfully push log entries to the aggregator, such as log formatting, Filebeat configuration (endpoints, certificates) and log browsing in Logstash.

- Date: November 20th, 2020
- Presenter: Georgios Papanikos (CITE)

2.3.8.3. C3.1 AI Gateway and ADAM API

This session **addressed core service C2, the Data Exploration Service**, in particular its three components: the Explorer, Jupyter Hub, and ADAM API. The live demonstration showcased an example on the Jupyter environment describing the four steps that constitute the typical workflow of ADAM API: user authentication, retrieval of datasets from registered endpoints, search for specific data products and access to the data.

- Date: November 19th, 2020
- Presenter: Simone Mantovani (MEE0)
- Available demo material: [ADAM API](#)

2.3.8.4. C3.3 Horovod service (3rd Project meeting, 19 NOV 2020)

In this session, a short demo of the Horovod service was presented, **introducing a project-level, scalable solution for distributed training of deep learning models**, exploitable by all the thematic services. The demo focused on how to access the Horovod cluster through Jupyter Hub to execute model training tasks using the Tensorflow and Keras libraries. The system architecture and deployment specifications were explained.

- Date: November 19th, 2020.
- Presenter: Attila Farkas (SZTAKI)
- Available demo material: [Distributed Deep Learning-Horovod](#)

2.3.8.5. Visual Discovery framework integration to Visualization Gateway

This live demonstration showed working examples on JupyterHub of **two fundamental pieces of the Visual Discovery framework**: VisIVO, the core visualization package; and Splotch, a high-performance particle visualizer. The two services are part of the Visualization Gateway, accessible by all thematic services.

- Date: November 19th, 2020.
- Presenter: Eva Sciacca (INAF)
- Available demo material: [VDFramework](#)

2.3.8.6. Spark demonstration

This demonstration showed a practical use case of the Spark core service for hyperparameter optimisation, applicable to machine learning tasks of the thematic services.

- Date: January 22th, 2021
- Presenter: T. Ceconello (UNIMIB)

2.4. Thematic Services Internal Validation

In the context of the 1st release of NEANIAS thematic services, that took place on November 2020 (M12), internal validation sessions on the thematic services were performed to evaluate functionalities and maturity. The validation process involved a total of 108 end-users from the target communities, namely underwater, atmospheric and space. The validators, selected by the service providers, spanned a wide range of technical profiles, including students, academics, researchers and industry professionals. In total, 28 end-users validated the underwater services; 30 end-users validated the atmospheric services, and 50 end-users validated the space services, reaching a basis of 10 users for almost all services. The validation results were predominantly positive, allowing service providers to spot bugs and issues affecting performance and stability, that were promptly resolved. Moreover, the validation process provided specific, valuable first-hand feedback on how to improve the thematic services according to the needs of the target communities, both from a functional and UX point of view.

Reports summarizing the validation results and feedback received for each service are available in the corresponding deliverables D2.4 [1] (underwater), D3.4 [2] (atmospheric) and D4.4 [3] (space).

3. External Onboarding and Training Activities

3.1. User board coordination

NEANIAS User Board foresees a series of actions, involving work packages 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6, to **increase visibility of the project and coordinate the engagement and onboarding** of external users. These activities, presented in [the project's General Meeting](#) hold in April 2021, include:

- Promoting the presentation of NEANIAS thematic services **in seminars and workshops**.
- Conducting a **second service validation round in May 2021**, involving external users from the target communities, up to 40 per thematic service, to reach a total of 600 users.
- Generating **multimedia material to increase the visibility of the developed services** within the target communities, such as video tutorials and demonstration videos with a scientific approach).

3.2. Thematic Services Onboarding and Training

Following the first release of NEANIAS thematic services, service providers and related Work Packages, in coordination with the NEANIAS User Board, have **planned a number of actions to increase the visibility of the NEANIAS service offerings** within the research ecosystem, engaging end-users from the target communities (underwater, atmospheric and space) and **drawing new potential users** from synergistic sectors and industries through the **joint development of new business opportunities**. These activities include the organisation of technical tutorials and webinars that connect users and service providers, the organization of multidisciplinary events such as Workshops and Hackathons, looking for potential applications that reach beyond the initial scope of the services, the participation in conferences and other scientific venues that highlight the potential of NEANIAS services, and the generation of detailed user documentation and support material that facilitates the onboarding process.

3.2.1. Underwater specific activities

NEANIAS underwater service providers onboarding activities comprise the co-hosting of the *Blue Research and Innovation Days* event and the organization of several practical sessions at universities focusing on the developed services.

3.2.1.1. Blue Week (Blue projects/ community)

During April 21st-23rd, NEANIAS co-hosted the "*Blue Research and Innovation Days*"⁴ event, together with other European and National (Greek) projects. The primary goal was **to create**

⁴ <https://blueinnovation2021.athenarc.gr/>

a forum of discussion, with more than 500 attendees, bringing together key actors from the scientific community and industry, to identify **overlapping working areas, create synergies and shape future activities focusing on 'Blue economy'**, i.e., the "sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and jobs while preserving the health of ocean ecosystem."⁵

Within the framework of this event, the developers of the underwater services (U1, U2, U3) provided a detailed presentation of their solutions by means of audiovisual material (presentations, live demonstrations), showcasing their capacities, current results and future perspectives, thus raising awareness and interest among the event participants.

NEANIAS also took part in the *Blue Hackathon*, a **2-day contest** aimed at data scientists, students, researchers and representatives from both private and public sectors, **focused on developing innovative solutions for blue-economy related challenges**. In particular, NEANIAS introduced two challenges based on services U1 and U3. The participants could access and use the tools to tackle problems like online image annotation of underwater images, and submarine cable route design.

3.2.1.2. U1 Practical Lesson

Practical lesson with undergraduate students from the University of Athens and the University of Milan, showing how they **can process the swath data** using service U1. 10 students used the service and produced their own bathymetric maps.

- Date: April, 2021
- Presenters: D. Lampridou (NKUA)

3.2.1.3. U2 Practical Lesson

Practical lesson with undergraduate students from the University of Girona, showing the **camera calibration task of service U2**. 60 students used the service and calibrated their own cameras.

- Date: March, 2021 (different practical sessions)
- Presenter: R.Garcia (CORONIS)

3.2.2. Atmospheric specific activities

Atmospheric thematic services onboarding activities have so far been focused on promoting the services by means of the following actions:

⁵ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/infographic/2017/06/06/blue-economy>

- Participation in webinars and events to promote the service developments and engage end-users to become aware and be a part of NEANIAS community
- Promotion of the project Open Call opportunities in WP5 activities

3.2.2.1. Production of training resources

WP3 service providers are planning the **production of a user guide** that explains how to use the ATMO-seism service and another guide that shows the use of the ATMO-stress service. This material will be available online for external users.

The service ATMO4CAST team will produce documentation on the usage of the service plus additional training material to engage students and researchers from the University of Aveiro, as well as ISMAI and Coimbra Business School, in order to assess its usability and accessibility and retrieve insights about the business adoption of such innovative service.

3.2.2.2. Practical Lessons

Practical lessons have been given to **undergraduate students from the University of Milan Bicocca**, showing how to construct the stress field trajectories from local measurements of tectonic and volcano tectonic features by using the NEANIAS WP3-A2 service ATMO-stress. Students used the service and reconstructed the stress field of some selected show cases.

- Date: March, 2021
- Presenter: A. Tibaldi (UNIMIB)

3.2.2.3. Participation in conferences and workshops

During the NEANIAS project, the WP3-A2 services will be promoted outside by means of oral and poster presentations at national and international scientific and technical conferences and workshops related to the Earth sciences community. Up to now, the ATMO-stress service has been showcased at the **vpPico Presentation in the EGU General Assembly 2021**, held online (19-30 April 2021), session TS 5.4 in the framework of the following three presentations:

- Falsaperla, S., Tibaldi, A., Corti, N., De Beni, E., Bonali, F. L., Langer, H., Neri, M., Cantarero, M., Reitano, D., and Fallati, L.: Multidisciplinary analyses for mapping and evaluating kinematics and stress/strain field at active faults and fissures at NE Rift, Mt Etna (Italy), EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-4279, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-4279>, 2021.
- Corti, N., Bonali, F. L., Tibaldi, A., Fallati, L., and Russo, E.: UAV-Based Structure-from-Motion Photogrammetry used for reconstructing Late Pleistocene-Holocene deformation: an example from Krafla Rift (NE Iceland), EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-3467, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-3467>, 2021.
- Russo, E., Corti, N., Bonali, F. L., Tibaldi, A., Pasquaré Mariotto, F., Fallati, L., and Marchese, F.: Reconstruction of the entire rift architecture of Theistareykir Fissure Swarm (northeast Iceland): integration between extensive UAV and field surveys, EGU

General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-5246, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-5246>, 2021.

The NEANIAS project has also been showcased at the **7th International Conference in Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management – GISTAM 2021** (23-25 April 2021, online streaming) in the framework of the presentation:

- Bonali, F., Fallati, L., Antoniou, V., Drymoni, K., Mariotto, F., Corti, N., Tibaldi, A., Gudmundsson, A. & Nomikou, P. (2021). Virtual Outcrops Building in Extreme Logistic Conditions for Data Collection, Geological Mapping, and Teaching: The Santorini's Caldera Case Study, Greece. In Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management - GISTAM, ISBN 978-989-758-503-6 ISSN 2184-500X, pages 67-74. DOI: 10.5220/0010419300670074.

The NEANIAS Project and its Atmospheric Services (namely A3 and ADAM platform) have been presented and promoted at **Milano Digital Week 2021**, organised between March 17th and 21st. The session entitled “DAI SERVIZI CLOUD PER LA SCIENZA APERTA ALLA SOSTENIBILITÀ”, organised by professor Giuseppe Vizzari where the value proposition of the thematic services was explained to a vast community of students and citizens from Milan, who were invited to experiment the services, provide feedback and participate in the project's open call.

3.2.3. Space specific activities

NEANIAS space service providers are taking active part in the effective dissemination of the project, increasing the penetration of the services within the European astrophysics and planetary science communities through a series of coordinated actions:

3.2.3.1. Production of training resources

Space service providers **envisage the production of abundant training resources and support material** that will be available online for external users. These include:

- Dedicated webinars for each space service, with a live demonstration showcasing its main functionalities by means of a real-world use case.
- Creation of User Cookbooks complementing the most technical documentation (available at <https://docs.neanias.eu/>), in order to facilitate the users' initial contact with the space services, by providing a simplified, step-by-step user guide.

3.2.3.2. Participation in conferences and workshops

During the project lifecycle, NEANIAS space services **will be promoted for onboarding by means of oral and poster contributions in renowned scientific and technical conferences** and workshops related to the astrophysics and planetary science community. As of M18, the events in which NEANIAS service offerings have been showcased are:

- Computing Conference 2020

Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)

- Dates: Jul 16th -17th , 2020
- Web: <https://saiconference.com/Computing>
- Contribution: "Towards porting Astrophysics Visual Analytics Services to the European Open Science Cloud" (E. Sciacca)
- European Astronomy Society Annual Meeting 2020
 - Dates: Jun 29th -Jul 3rd, 2020
 - Web: <https://eas.unige.ch/EAS2020/>
 - Contributions: "NEANIAS-Tackling the challenges of future astronomy" (C. Bordiu)
- Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XXX
 - Dates: Nov 8th -12th , 2020.
 - Web: <https://adass2020.es/>
 - Contributions: "Novel EOSC Services for Space challenges: the NEANIAS first outcomes" (E. Sciacca), "Astronomical research in the next decade: trends, barriers and needs in data access, management, visualization and analysis" (C. Bordiu)
- GARR Workshop 2020
 - Dates: Nov 2th-6th
 - Web: <https://www.eventi.garr.it/it/ws20>
 - Contribution: "INAF Sfide e Opportunità di Servizi per l'Astrofisica sulla Cloud GARR: NEANIAS e l'Integrazione in EOSC" (E. Sciacca)
- SPIE Astronomical telescopes and instrumentation
 - Dates: Dec 14th -18th, 2020
 - Web: <https://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/astronomical-telescopes-and-instrumentation>
 - Contributions: "Astrophysics Visual Analytics services on the European Open Science Cloud" (E. Sciacca).
- SKA science conference 2021
 - Dates: March 15th-19th , 2021
 - Web: <https://www.skatelescope.org/skascicon21/>
 - Contributions: "Searching and characterizing extended sources in the MeerKAT Galactic Plane Survey" (S. Riggi), "Astrophysics Visual Analytics Services on the Cloud for Open Science Toward SKA" (E. Sciacca), "Radio-astronomical image segmentation with Tiramisu and Mask R-CNN" (R. Sortino).
- Milano Digital Week 2021
 - Dates: March 17th-21st, 2021
 - Web: <https://www.milanodigitalweek.com/>
 - Contributions: "Portiamos gli astri sulla Cloud" (G. Vizzari)
- Applications of Statistical Methods and ML in the Space Sciences
 - Dates: May 17th-21st, 2021
 - Web: <http://spacescience.org/workshops/mlconference2021.php>
 - Contributions: "Towards a modern unsupervised ML approach to the analysis of astrophysics images" (T. Cecconello, C. Bordiu).

3.2.3.3. Collaboration with other European Projects

Exploitation of synergies with other European projects, such as ESCAPE - European Science Cluster for Astronomy and Particle Physics⁶ and ERC ECOGAL⁷ looking for **potential collaborations and joint initiatives** that benefit from common or shared thematic and target communities, with the goal of promoting the NEANIAS space services offerings reaching as many users as possible.

3.3. Core Services Onboarding

Core services are directly integrated into other core and thematic services. Consequently, the experiences of onboarding for Thematic services will be leveraged upon appropriately to develop them further, in order to build specific Core services onboarding activities. Such activities will be designed and carried out by WP6 partners in close collaboration with the Thematic Work Packages, with the aim of promoting jointly both the Core and Thematic service offerings of NEANIAS. Furthermore, the partners of WP6 will take every opportunity to advertise and promote the core services on various upcoming workshops, conferences and events to raise awareness and interest. Direct communication (advertisements) towards potential scientific groups and communities (which are closely related to the WP6 partners) will also be initiated.

In this respect, *Artificial Intelligence (C3)* and *Visualization (C4)* core services have a particular attractiveness for external users. Owing to their general-purpose, traversal nature, these services can be easily adapted or extended beyond their original scope (e.g. to visualize or analyse other types of scientific data, not necessarily related to Underwater, Atmospheric or Space sectors). This enormously facilitates the design of specific onboarding strategies, highlighting the potential of these and their successful application to the NEANIAS science use cases. These strategies may involve a number of complementary actions, including but not limited to:

- **targeted advertisement toward specific groups** of potential users interested in novel developments on Visualization, Data Analysis and Machine Learning (both from academic and industry sectors).
- Participation and promotion of the services in **generalist Computer Vision, AI and ML conferences and workshops**.
- **organization of hackathons** and data challenges to explore and exploit the possibilities of these services in innovative ways.

⁶ <https://projectescape.eu/>

⁷ <http://www.ecogal.eu/>

3.4. Business opportunities and innovation (Open Call)

To **boost the development of new business opportunities and accelerate the onboarding of external users** into the project, NEANIAS has organized its first Open Call for Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Science initiatives. European Start-ups often face difficulties in the early phases, mostly because of the lack of high-quality infrastructure and human resources available to test and efficiently develop their technology. NEANIAS aims to provide technical and financial support to tackle these challenges. **The purpose of this Open Call is to spark and support the development of a wide variety of innovation projects**, by providing novel services created in the frame of the NEANIAS project, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and contributing to advance research and innovation in Europe. The overarching goal is to build up and strengthen the European innovation community by identifying and supporting innovative projects with novel services developed in the Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research fields. Innovation in this scope may refer to (a) new operation models for existing services, that can exploit NEANIAS resources (b) improving existing services utilizing NEANIAS offerings to increase their overall offering (c) brand new services inspired by NEANIAS offerings (d) new services in need offerings such as NEANIAS and EOSC ones, and many more. Award winners will have to show strong reuse of NEANIAS offerings and valid sustainability potential.

The first Open Call was launched on the 8 February 2021 and was closed on the 9 April 2021. NEANIAS Partners conducted a centralised effort in terms of communication and to provide all information about the opportunity in applying for the Open Call.

Target groups, reached out by NEANIAS experts:

- Start-ups
- Established private companies from diverse industries (SMEs / Multinationals)
- Groups of individual researchers / innovators of up to 3 members

The added values of NEANIAS were communicated by each Thematic sector representatives to their target audience.

As a result of the **intense communication campaign**, and individual discussions with potential applicants, altogether 19 eligible applications arrived (1 more application was submitted late, and 1 application neither indicate his clear interest in NEANIAS services nor indicated the thematic sector he belongs to:

Table 1: The Number of Applications per Thematic Sector – First round of Open Call

Thematic sector	No. of Applications
Atmospheric	5
Space	7
Underwater	7
Sum	19

Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)

The first round of selection of applications has been concluded on April 27th, 2021, with the participation of the Open Call Evaluation Board. In the next round, **the applicants are invited for an interview with the assigned NEANIAS experts** to provide further information about their project and discuss about the possible collaboration opportunities.

The final selection of the winners takes place until May 10th, then the collaboration will start between the selected applicants and the NEANIAS experts.

The provided services by NEANIAS for the winners of the Open Call:

- Access to NEANIAS Thematic Services
- Support on business development
- Networking
- Promotion

4. Conclusions and Future Steps

This deliverable summarizes the current status and future perspectives regarding training and user onboarding activities in NEANIAS. These activities **foster awareness raising and capacity delivery** on NEANIAS service offerings, highlighting the potential of the developed services for the target research communities, and contributing to the creation of a **solid and growing user base**.

In the course of the project, multiple training and onboarding activities have been successfully implemented, bringing together the relevant actors in the services' lifecycle, i.e. internal users (developers/providers) and external (end) users, allowing for raising interest, providing technical training and acquiring valuable inputs and feedback. However, besides the development and delivery of cutting-edge technological solutions for the underwater, atmospheric and space research communities, **NEANIAS seeks to onboard these communities onto the Open Science paradigm**, introducing researchers to the benefits of collaborative and reproducible science in the EOSC framework. By embracing open science practices, research communities will **unlock new opportunities and discoveries**, only possible through a close collaboration across diverse areas. NEANIAS will thus **strengthen research communities** both directly, by means of its service offerings, and indirectly, through the nurturing of the concepts that support the interdisciplinary research era.

The long-term sustainability of NEANIAS service offerings depends on the **development of reliable onboarding strategies** that contribute to enlarge and support the NEANIAS (and EOSC) user base, also facilitating the **communication between target communities and service providers**. Indeed, feedback from end-users is critical for the Technical and Strategy boards in order to fine tune the services' capabilities to the ever-increasing, ever-evolving needs of the research communities. The successful materialization of a collaborative research ecosystem requires a **compromise between service providers, stakeholders and policy-makers** to produce a suitable framework that encourages and supports researchers in the adoption of Open Science practices and FAIR principles. In this context, aspects such as a close contact with universities and research institutions, the recurrent organization and participation of NEANIAS in events such as the Blue Research and Innovation Week, or the exploitation of synergies with other European projects and initiatives bound to the Open Science paradigm, are of the utmost importance to bridge the current gap between the research community and the Open Science paradigm.

References

- [1] NEANIAS WP2 Collaboration, "D2.4 - Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services (Release #1)", NEANIAS, 2020 ([link](#))
- [2] NEANIAS WP3 Collaboration, "D3.4 - 3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)", NEANIAS, 2020 ([link](#))
- [3] NEANIAS WP4, "D4.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services (Release #1)", NEANIAS, 2020 ([link](#))

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ML	Machine Learning
REST	Representational State Transfer
RDM	Research Data Management
SKA	Square Kilometre Array
SME	Small & Medium Enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level